

BUCKLING OF PRESSURE VESSELS UNDER MANUFACTURING STRESSES

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this paper is to investigate the possibility of buckling of filament wound pressure vessels due to manufacturing induced stresses. Vessels both without and with metal lining are considered. The wall of the vessel may buckle due to manufacturing stresses even in the absence of externally applied loads. Sample results are presented which illustrate the influence of various design parameters, (e.g. winding angle, wall thickness) on the critical buckling load.

INTRODUCTION

Every housewife knows that sausages crack longitudinally during cooking. The reason is very simple: in cylinders, loaded by internal pressure, the hoop stresses are twice as large as the longitudinal ones. If the material of the cylinder is isotropic, the failure occurs by a crack perpendicular to the maximum stress.

Pressure vessels consisting of a cylinder in the middle and two hemispheres at the ends are very commonly used structures. Composites, i.e., fiber reinforced plastics, are excellent candidate to manufacture pressure vessels, because it can be applied in such a way that the strength in the circumferential direction is twice of that in the longitudinal direction.

Composite pressure vessels are often manufactured by filament winding. During this process tensile stress is applied on the wound fibers which causes manufacturing stresses in the composite cylinder.

After filament winding the cylinder is cured in an autoclave. Because of the change in temperature (and chemical shrinkage) additional stresses arise in the cylinder.

The question arises: could these stresses cause the buckling of the pressure vessel without applying any external load?

STRESSES IN A CYLINDER MADE OF ALUMINUM AND REINFORCED PLASTIC

In filament wound composite pressure vessels the aluminum mold often serves also as the load bearing inner part of the vessel (Fig. 1).

Composites have high strength and relatively low stiffness, hence the aluminum yields when the stress of the composite is only a fraction of its strength (Fig. 2). The performance, i.e. the load bearing capacity without yielding, could be improved in the following way [1]:

Figure 1. The built-up of the cylindrical pressure vessel

Figure 2. Elastic behavior of aluminum and composite

Figure 3. Behavior of a pressure vessel before and after pre-loading

The filament wound structure is pre-loaded while the aluminum is yielding but the composite still remains elastic (Fig. 3a, solid line). After removing the load (Fig. 3a, dashed line), residual stresses arise in the structure: compression develops in the aluminum and tension in the reinforced plastic. The resultant of the two is a bending moment (Fig. 4).

These stresses improve the load bearing capacity of the pressure vessel. If we load the pressure vessel again, higher internal pressure could be reached while both the aluminum and the reinforced plastic remain elastic (Fig. 3b).

However the question mentioned before arises: could these stresses (e.g., self bending moments) cause the buckling of the pressure vessel without applying any external load?

We will answer this question in the following.

Figure 4. The bending moment in the wall of pressure vessel induced by manufacturing stresses

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Let us consider the cylinder shown in Fig. 1, the wall of which consists of an arbitrary number of anisotropic layers. The layers could be homogeneous or made out of fiber reinforced plastic with arbitrary fiber orientation.

In the wall of the cylinder, due to manufacturing, internal stresses arise, the resultants of which are denoted by

$$M_x, M_y,$$

where M_x is the axial and M_y is the hoop bending moment. (The bending moment is considered positive if it causes compression in the inner side of the cylinder). Our aim is to determine the critical value of the bending moment (induced by manufacturing stresses).

THE CRITICAL LOAD OF THE CYLINDER

The author gave in a previous article [2] an analytical solution for the critical load parameter of anisotropic cylinders subjected to both external loads (pressure, torque) and internal (temperature) stresses. A computer code was also developed, designated as SHEBU (shell buckling), to perform the numerical calculation, and approximate expressions were derived assuming an equivalent isotropic shell.

In his work the author assumed that the material of the shell is linearly elastic and the deformations are small. The assumptions of the thin shell theory [3] were applied, neglecting the transverse shear deformation.

Approximate expression for the critical load parameter. The expressions for the critical buckling load can be simplified assuming that the wall of the cylinder is isotropic and the wall thickness is very thin. Here we give the expressions only for two special load-cases, the general loading can be found in [2]. If an *axial load* acts on the cylinder, the classical critical axial force is

$$N_{cr} = -\frac{2}{R} \sqrt{DT(1 - \nu^2)},$$

where R is the radius of the cylinder, D and T are the bending and tensile stiffnesses of the shell, which are for a homogeneous isotropic wall:

$$D = \frac{Et^3}{12(1-\nu^2)}, \quad T = \frac{Et}{1-\nu^2},$$

E is Young's modulus, t is the wall thickness and ν is Poisson's ratio. This result of N_{cr} of course agrees with that to be found in the literature [3].

If a *hoop bending moment* arises in the cylinder (in the case of manufacturing stresses we are interested in these), the critical value of the hoop bending moment is [2]:

$$M_{cr}^{appr} = 2\sqrt{DT(1-\nu^2)}.$$

The buckling shape is axisymmetrical, the half wavelength in the axial direction is $l_x = \pi\sqrt{D/T(1+\nu^2)}$.

These results obtained for isotropic cylinders could be used as approximations for pressure vessels of arbitrary layups.

SAMPLE PROBLEMS

The results summarized in the previous section are applicable for pressure vessels subjected to manufacturing stresses. In the following we will assume that the aluminum and the composite work together without any slip, and that buckles develop in the cylinder far from the hemispheres.

Figure 5. Geometry of pressure vessel

The geometry of the pressure vessel in question can be seen in Fig. 5 [1], the material properties are given in Table 1. Pressure vessels of this kind were tested at the Technical University of Budapest [1].

The calculation of the critical bending moment was performed using the SHEBU code [2]. The first step is to determine the stiffness matrix of the wall using the laminated plate theory [4]. The tensile stiffnesses (**A**), flexural stiffnesses (**D**), and the coupling terms (**B**) are given in Table 2. Further details of the calculation are not presented, only the critical bending moment.

Table 1. Material properties of E-glass/epoxy composite and Aluminum used in the sample problems

E-glass/epoxy composites:	
longitudinal Young's modulus	$E_x=38.6$ GPa
transverse in-plane Young's modulus	$E_y=8.27$ GPa
shear modulus	$G_{xy}=4.14$ GPa
Poisson's ratio	$\nu_{yz}=0.4$
longitudinal strength	$X=1.062$ MPa
Aluminum:	
Young's modulus	$E_x=73.0$ GPa
Poisson's ratio	$\nu_{yz}=0.33$
longitudinal strength	$X=0.62$ GPa

Table 2. The **A**, **B**, and **D** matrices in the stiffness matrix

$$A = 10^8 \begin{bmatrix} 7.305 & 2.520 & & \\ 2.520 & 8.222 & & \\ & & & 2.788 \end{bmatrix} \text{N/m}, \quad B = -10^5 \begin{bmatrix} 29.798 & 8.399 & & \\ 8.399 & 19.906 & & \\ & & & 7.779 \end{bmatrix} \text{N}$$

$$D = 10^3 \begin{bmatrix} 25.073 & 8.876 & & \\ 8.876 & 30.785 & & \\ & & & 95.459 \end{bmatrix} \text{Nm}$$

The calculation of the critical bending moment was performed for two cases: i) there are only hoop bending moments (M_y) in the cylinder, ii) there are both hoop and axial bending moments of equal magnitude in the cylinder ($M_x=M_y$). The results are

$$M_{cr}=6.54 \cdot 10^6 \text{ N}, \quad l_x=0.1585 \text{ m}, \quad l_y= \infty,$$

for both case i) and case ii).

Let us determine the maximum possible hoop moment in the wall of the cylinder due to manufacturing stresses. If the aluminum yields in compression, the bending moment arising in the wall is as follows:

$$M \approx 6.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m} \times 0.62 \times 10^9 \frac{18.82}{2} \frac{\text{N}}{\text{m}^2} \times 10^{-3} \text{ m} = 3.79 \times 10^4 \text{ N}$$

This is less by two orders of magnitude than the critical bending moment. (Note that we assumed: there is no separation between the aluminum and the composite.)

Let us approximate the critical bending moment using the formulas derived for isotropic cylinders. The bending and tensile stiffnesses of the shell are calculated as the geometrical means of the elements (1,1) and (2,2) of matrices **D** and **A**, respectively:

$$D = \sqrt{25.07 \times 30.979} \times 10^3 = 27.78 \times 10^3 \text{ Nm}, \quad T = \sqrt{7.305 \times 8.222} \times 10^8 = 7.750 \times 10^8 \text{ N / m}$$

and Poisson's ratio is taken to $\nu=0.33$. The approximate critical bending moment is as follows:

$$M_{cr}^{appr} = 2\sqrt{27.78 \times 10^3 \times 7.750 \times 10^8 (1 - 0.33^2)} = 8.76 \times 10^6 \text{ N.}$$

The approximate critical load (calculated on an isotropic shell) overestimate the critical load by 30%.

In Fig. 6 the effect of the thickness of the aluminum mold on the critical bending moment was investigated. The radius of the cylinder is $R = 0.1521$ m. The approximate critical load calculated on an isotropic cylinder is also shown in the Figure.

Figure 6. Effect of liner thickness on the critical bending moment

The effect of the ply angle of an "angle ply" composite cylinder was investigated in Fig. 7. The radius of the cylinder is $R=0.1521$ m, the wall thickness is $t=16$ mm.

Figure 7. Effect of liner thickness on the critical bending moment

CONCLUSIONS

The buckling of composite pressure vessels containing also aluminum liners due to manufacturing stresses was investigated applying a method (and a computer program) presented in [2]. It was found that the safety against buckling due to the manufacturing stresses is significantly high.

Very simple formulas were also derived to calculate the critical bending moment of isotropic cylinders. These formulas were used to approximate the critical load of anisotropic cylinders and it was found that in the investigated cases the difference between the 'exact' and approximate values is less than 30%.

List of References

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